

The background of the cover features an aerial photograph of a river winding through a dry, brown landscape. The river is a vibrant blue-green color. In the bottom right corner, there is a dark blue area with a white grid and a white line graph showing an upward trend, symbolizing data and climate change.

International Scientific and Practical Conference

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

May 19, 2026

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

WICAR-2026

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International Scientific and Practical Conference -2026

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference innovative approaches to water resource management in arid regions in the context of climate change on May 19, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The conference aims to discuss key issues of effective water resource management in arid regions under climate change, develop and apply innovative approaches and mathematical and computational modeling methods, share recent research results and practical experience, and strengthen international academic cooperation in this field.

Key Themes of the Conference:

1. Water Diplomacy and Integrated Approaches in International Relation: Interdisciplinary Approaches to Sustainable Development, Communication and Global Security

- Issues of systemic analysis in international relations and world politics in the context of water diplomacy
- Economic, environmental and energy aspects of sustainable development
- Systemic approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

2. Mathematical and computer modeling of optimal water resources management under climate change

- Optimal water resource management under climate change
- Modeling water resource dynamics and climate variability
- Methods of applied and computational mathematics in irrigation system modeling.

3. Environmental and Hydrogeological Processes in the Aral Sea Region: Analysis Based on Modern Technologies

- Analysis of hydrogeological processes in the Aral Sea region
- Application of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data technologies to environmental challenges
- Simulation and stochastic modeling of environmental and hydrogeological processes in the Aral region.

The event was conducted in a hybrid format with participation in English, Russian, and Uzbek. The conference provided a high-level platform for scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Implementing the Water–energy–food (WEF) Nexus Approach to Address Water Scarcity in Central Asia

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Introduction

Since the Soviet era, the Central Asian republics – Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan – have been locked in a "geographical trap" regarding water distribution. This interdependence was managed through a strategic "barter system" designed to overcome the region's unique topography. The upstream countries (Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan) control the headwaters of the Amu Darya and Syr Darya but lack the flat land required for large-scale farming. Conversely, the downstream states (Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, and Kazakhstan) possess fertile plains but lack independent water sources. During the summer months, upstream states would release water to support downstream agriculture, generating hydroelectricity in the process. In winter, to allow upstream reservoirs to refill, downstream states would provide natural gas, fuel oil, and coal to the mountain regions to prevent freezing. However, following independence, this barter system collapsed as market-priced hydrocarbons and geopolitical tensions led to a breakdown in cooperation.

The most significant breakdown was seen during the period of building the Roghun HPP, between Uzbekistan and Tajikistan. Regarding the background of the issue, the construction of the Roghun Hydroelectric Power Plant was approved by the USSR State Construction Committee and began in 1987. The project of the station was developed by the Tashkent-based institute "Hydroproject," taking into account not only the energy needs of Tajikistan, but also the irrigated agriculture of Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan. Interestingly, at that time Uzbekistan, guided by plans to increase cotton production, supported the project, while the Tajik public opposed it, as the construction could have harmed the environment of Tajikistan and undermined public health. Twenty years later, however, Tashkent strongly rejected the resumption of the construction of this hydroelectric power plant, insisting on a preliminary international assessment and the provision of technically substantiated written guarantees from international experts confirming that the dam will be safe. As for the assessments carried out during the Soviet period, they are also not satisfactory to Tashkent, since at that time, as stated in an article in an Uzbek newspaper, "independent auditing and independent expert evaluation were not practiced." There is also a view, actively supported by Uzbekistan, that the tragedy of the Aral Sea is primarily caused by hydroelectric power plants built on the rivers of Amu Darya and Syr Darya that feed it. The Roghun project would further aggravate this problem. Tashkent had another concern. It is that, by regulating water releases at the Roghun Hydroelectric Power Plant, Dushanbe would be able to limit the volume of water used by Uzbekistan and thereby dictate its terms in various disputes.

Tajikistan has its own arguments in response to all these claims. Tajik experts assert that the Roghun Hydroelectric Power Plant will only benefit Uzbekistan, and that all Uzbek protests are linked to a reluctance to see the Tajik people become less dependent on Uzbekistan. They argue that this opposition is a political move by the Uzbek leadership aimed at preventing the development of Tajikistan. From Dushanbe's perspective, the Aral Sea crisis is primarily the fault of the downstream countries, which use water resources inefficiently. The problem is further exacerbated, Tajik officials note, by the construction of massive reservoirs in those regions, whose

total capacity is one and a half times greater than the current volume of the Aral Sea [13]. The disputes surrounding the Roghun Hydroelectric Power Plant were just one, but a vivid example of the struggle for water resources among the countries of the Central Asian region.

Although in recent years Central Asian countries signed a series of protocols that act as a modern version of the old barter system, the nature of the water crisis has shifted. The question is no longer about how to distribute water effectively, but how it can be conserved sufficiently to withstand the dual pressures of climate change and rapid demographic growth.

Literature Review

United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) is implementing the energy-water-land nexus approach in a Consortium, which is led by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). This is because about a quarter of the working population in Central Asia relies on agriculture as a source of livelihood, but minimal precipitation means that irrigation must be supplied from rivers, which are increasingly being used for energy generation. New hydroelectric power plants built on the Amu Darya and Syr Darya rivers may disrupt water flow to downstream regions that depend on these rivers for crop irrigation, livestock maintenance, and socio-economic development. This highlights that the water crisis is not the isolated problem, but rather forms a “triangle” with energy and food production.

While international organizations promote the nexus approach, scholarly analysis reveals gaps in the adoption of this method. The WEF nexus presents opportunities for policy makers, business leaders, investors, nongovernmental organizations and the public at large to address three mutually-dependent global security concerns (i.e. access to water, sustainable energy and food security). However, several challenges remain for the corresponding research required for sound operationalization of the nexus. These are largely reflected by considerable data and knowledge gaps and lack of systematic analytical tools to apply nexus thinking effectively [8]. Another challenge is identified by I.Abdullaev and Sh.Rakhmatullaev, who argue that hydrocracies (water bureaucracies) are still hesitant to share with other sectors their area of expertise in decision-making power over affairs of water resources management. Moreover, the capacities of the national partners are limited by the sectoral distribution culminating in “egocentrism” [1]. This demonstrates that although the governments acknowledge the need to overcome “water box” problem, some aspects of nexus approach still require further development and reform.

Another group of scholars discusses the benefits of the WEF nexus approach in achieving the SDGs. Poverty eradication is the overarching target of the SDGs with an overall commitment to “free humanity from poverty and hunger as a matter of urgency. Sustained poverty eradication is also a central goal of sustainable livelihoods approaches in recognition that sustainable and fulfilling livelihoods are critical to breaking the poverty cycle. It therefore seems crucial to consider livelihoods more explicitly when presenting a set of global targets to achieve future sustainable development of society as a whole. Water, energy and food security are key focal elements for reducing poverty by ensuring adequate resources for sustaining and improving livelihoods in equitable ways [4]. The ongoing development and formulation of the Sustainable Development Goals should consider and recognize the importance of a nexus approach to water, energy and food. Doing so will help promote consistency and complementarity among the Sustainable Development Goals. The goals should reflect nexus interactions that can be monitored at different scales to increase the benefits for both humans and nature [2].

Methodology

This study employs the qualitative research design to evaluate the Water-Energy-Food (WEF) nexus approach as a solution for water scarcity in Central Asia. The methodology is divided

into three phases. First, a thematic analysis of scholarly literature review will demonstrate the effectiveness of nexus approach to demonstrate its theoretical validity, Second, the study uses the Aral Sea crisis as a case study, by analyzing historical data and academic arguments, it shows the consequences of treating the water problem as an “isolated” one. Finally, the research gathers data from intergovernmental organizations (e.g., World Bank, UNECE) to identify practical techniques for integrated resource management in arid climates.

Findings

The word 'nexus' (derived from the Latin word *nectare*, meaning 'to connect') means an important connection between the parts of a system or a group of things [3]. ‘Nexus thinking’ was first conceived by the World Economic Forum to promote the inseparable links between the use of resources to provide basic and universal rights to food, water and energy security. Whilst the World Economic Forum presented the nexus framework from a securities perspective (water–energy–food security), subsequent versions have taken on various facets with alternative components, such as water resources as a central component, land use–water–energy and food as a core component with land–water–energy linkages. Nexus thinking is advocated as an advance on current and often sector-specific governance of natural resource use [4].

Apart from the resource-centric nexuses (like Water-Energy-Food), there is also the nexus which aims to stabilize the region after the crisis, during the fragile periods – The Humanitarian - Development-Peace (HDP) nexus. In an attempt to address the causes and effects of crises, international, intergovernmental and non-governmental organizations intervene in such protracted situations, aiming to save lives, alleviate suffering, mitigate risks and pave the way for durable solutions. The Humanitarian-Development-Peace (HDP) nexus is the most recent proposition for a comprehensive response to protracted crises and has been piloted in a variety of contexts, particularly in protracted displacement situations. According to the Development Assistance Committee (DAC) of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the nexus aims to strengthen “collaboration, coherence and complementarity” between humanitarian, development and peace interventions “to reduce overall vulnerability and the number of unmet needs, strengthen risk management capacities and address root causes of conflict [11]. This can show that the nexus approach is increasingly being integrated in all spheres of life, recognizing that complex crises cannot be solved by a single sector in isolation.

The Aral Sea case study can serve as an excellent example of the failure to recognize the interconnection between water sustainability and large-scale agriculture. During the Soviet era, the Central Asian Republics (CARs) were ruled under management of centralized Soviet Union. Economically, the region was untapped until Nikita Khrushchev executed the “Virgin Land” policy. The purpose of this policy was to focus on agricultural productivity as a means of economic prosperity [9]. This harmonic balance of water resources changed when the Soviet Union decided to expand irrigation lands for the cultivation of cotton within Central Asian downstream countries (Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan). Soviet planners emphasized on mono-cultural cotton production than crops which fit the climate condition of the region. As a result of irrational irrigation, Aral Sea received less than 1000 km³ of water flow in the last 35 years leading to the sharp decline of water level in the Aral Sea [10]. The Aral Sea and its surroundings have been greatly affected by climate variability and environmental changes which occur at different spatial and temporal scales. There is a complex connection between climate, hydrology and land-use. Any change in one of these systems will trigger changes in the other. For instance, changes in hydrological patterns and surface coverage of a basin result in changes in temperature and precipitation [7]. Lioubimtseva

in her research found another interconnection that was also vital to understand before implementing the “Cotton first” policy.

Conclusion & Discussion

Addressing water scarcity in Central Asia requires a holistic approach that integrates food and energy security, as these sectors are interconnected (see Fig.1). Innovative technologies must be deployed to optimize resource efficiency and mitigate water loss.

Currently, irrigated agriculture consumes approximately 90 percent of all abstracted water in the Aral Sea Basin, where Central Asian countries are located. A combination of high levels of water withdrawals and already limited water resources puts considerable stress on the water supply in the region. If no improvements in productivity of water are achieved, the likely increases in water abstractions and additional water storage in the upstream countries are likely to lead to increased seasonal water shortages in irrigation water supply in downstream countries of the basin, thereby negatively affecting agricultural production and rural livelihoods and intensifying out-migration to urban areas. Modernization of irrigation systems in the region is emerging as a key solution for responding to the challenges in the sector under the changing socioeconomic circumstances. Technological advances and innovations made over the past few decades have resulted in significant improvements in the efficiency of irrigation systems and the quality of their performance. This includes a range of modern technologies that incorporate, among other things: pipe distribution systems combined with pressurized irrigation (drip and sprinkler irrigation), ET-based water management using remote sensing, geographic information systems (GIS), digital and wireless communication of data and information, and SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) systems for canal control [12]. This can demonstrate that further investment on modernizing the irrigation system can lead to the reduction of water waste, thereby gradually solving the problem of water shortages in Central Asia.

Figure 1. The Nexus approach. Source: Global Water Partnership-Mediterranean (2019) [5].

The reliance on hydropower makes energy systems in Central Asia vulnerable to fluctuations in water availability. This vulnerability is evident in Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan, where significant fluctuations in annual electricity production are notable and the seasonal variability of

hydropower poses significant challenges to meeting peak demand. These challenges may intensify with an increasing share of hydropower in the energy mix. While large reservoirs can partially mitigate such variability to a certain degree, they lead to environmental and social challenges. To address the remaining dependence on natural water availability, the integration of other non-hydro renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind is essential. Although they have emerged as promising alternatives, their contribution to the region's primary energy supply remains negligible at present [6]. Further research can focus on strategies to expand the integration of non-hydro renewable energy sources, while reducing the heavy reliance on hydropower.

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